

doi 10.5281/zenodo.8419038

Vol. 06 Issue 09 Sept - 2023

Manuscript ID: #01035

Metacognition and Performances of Literary Translation Students per Language Combination at the Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the metacognition and performance of French A and English Aliterary translation learners. The objectives were to investigate the degree of metacognitive awareness of the class of literary translation learners in general; and to find out if there are significant differences in metacognition and performance among the subjects based on language combination. It was hypothesised that there is a high degree of metacognitive awareness in the class of literary translation learners in general; and that French A literary translation learners do not demonstrate a significant difference in metacognitive awareness and performance than their English A counterparts. The Learning Theory (Constructivism) underpinned this research. It explained how subjects processed and retained information differently during learning. The research design was a non-intervention case study, which involved an intensive, systematic investigation without manipulating behaviour. Non-probability sampling was used to select 50 subjects, out of which outliers were eliminated and a homogenous group of 32 subjects who scored from 15 to 17 on 20 in a pre-test was retained. Qualitative data were culled through non-participant observation and Shraw & Denison's (1994) Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI) to investigate respondents' metacognitive knowledge and regulation. However, instead of declarations of true or false questions, the MAI was adapted and rephrased as close-ended questions to elicit responses designed on a 7-point Likert scale for frequency. Through this psychometric rating scale, responders specified the frequency with which they regulated cognition (by planning, managing information, monitoring understanding, correcting performance errors or evaluating their own learning) or demonstrated that they possess knowledge about cognition (by establishing that they possess declarative, procedural or conditional knowledge). In addition, a formative assessment test was administered to gauge performance in literary translation by the two groups. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation and inferential statistics (Independent Sample T-Test). The T-test was used to compare the metacognition test score of the students by language combination for significant difference. The results were presented on frequency distribution tables and on figures. The findings revealed that the metacognitive awareness French A learners is not significantly higher than that of English A learners and both groups performed the same in literary translation learning. The study recommended that English A learners should adopt some strategies to enhance their metacognitive abilities to be on the par with French A learners. It also recommended that both groups should adopt innovative learning strategies that will work in favour of their ability to predict how well they can perform literary translation tasks. Moreover, it was recommended to teachers that they should consider the inherent differences between learners in the literary translation classroom to ensure that their methods accommodate the less metacognitively aware group in the class. The implication of this study to literary translation teaching is that it will lay greater emphasis on enhancing students' metacognitive competence to boost learners' confidence about their learning.

KEYWORDS: Metacognition, Performance, Literary Translation Learners, ASTI.

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1.0 Introduction

Due to the exponential growth in the number of higher education institutions that are involved in translator training in Cameroon, ASTI is no longer enjoying the monopoly that it had always enjoyed when it existed as the pioneer and only translator training institution in the country for more than two and a half decades. Increasingly, the institution is beginning to bow under the pressure of moving towards a training model that places greater emphasis on training translators that will be more productive, competitive and employable, whose prospects will be significantly boosted in the existence of stiff competition.

Students who come to study translation at ASTI usually belong to two main language combinations, which are English A-French B and French A-English B. the former is the appellation for learners who have English as their language of instruction, while the latter refers to those who have French. Hence, the translation classroom in this institution is a linguistically learning space that is characterised by learning diversity. Learning diversity is an effect of life experiences that shapes the way individual students approach learning. In fact, due to the existence of learning diversity, it is necessary teachers to strive to meet the expectations of their students, such that everyone can derive fulfilment in the learning experience. In fact, such diversity can lead to differences in the way individuals process information and learn. Indeed, different factors that shape diversity, such as socio-economic background, language, gender, age, etc. work together to condition the way students learn. Hence, it is imperative to study and understand metacognition among these students and investigate how it can possibly impact performance in literary translation learning. Understanding metacognition of learners is a way to assisting them in developing their metacognitive abilities, not only to enable these trainee translators to become reflective learners, but to empower them to acquire learning strategies that will enable them to become more mindful learners (Sajna & Premachandran 2016:165).

1.1 The Problem

In fact, from non-participant observation and through experience gained from teaching translation at The Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters (ASTI) for the past twelve years, it has been observed that French A student translators perform better in literary translation learning than their English A counterparts. The rationale of the study is thus to establish if differences in academic performance are a direct consequence of different degrees of metacognitive awareness among student literary translators who belong to the two language combinations. The goal of this case study, therefore, is to examine if literary translation learners' knowledge about their strengths and weaknesses as well as their control of their individual cognitive strategies, differ per language combination. The study also seeks to understand how the above differences impact literary translation learners' respective performances.

1.2 Objectives

The study seeks to meet the following specific objectives:

- 1) To investigate the degree of metacognitive awareness of the class of literary translation learners in general.
- 2) To find out if there are any differences in metacognitive awareness and performance among the students based on language combination.

1.3 Hypotheses

It is therefore hypothesised in this study that:

- 1) There is a low degree of metacognitive awareness in the class of literary translation learners in general.

- 2) French A literary translation learners do not demonstrate a different in metacognitive awareness and performance from their English A counterparts.

1.4 Key Concepts

Four key concepts of this study, namely the Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters, metacognition, performance, translation and literary translation learners are defined in the sections below.

1.4.1 Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters

The Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters (ASTI) of the University of Buea is the first ever institution created in 1985 to train translators in Cameroon, a bilingual country with English and French as its official languages. ASTI remained the sole establishment of the Buea University Centre until 1993, when by decree N° 92/074 of 13 April 1992, it was transformed into a full-fledged University. Entrance into the Master of Arts in Translation at ASTI is gained through a competitive examination. The candidates who are eligible to sit for this examination are bachelor's degree holders who are generally two linguistically diverse sets of students. Some are learners with English as their A language, from the English sub-system of education, while others have French as their A language, from the French sub-system.

1.4.2 Metacognition

Metacognition is a regulatory system that helps learners understand and control their cognitive performance, such that they can take control of their learning and become an audience of their own intellectual performance (Sajna & Premachandran 2016:165). In other words, it is the ability of learners to understand what they know, so that they can take full control of their learning. Metacognition is knowledge about the regulation of an individual's cognitive abilities in a situation of learning, which helps them understand how they learn best, know their limits and create means of supporting their learning. Metacognitive knowledge is threefold and encompasses awareness of knowledge, awareness of thinking and awareness of thinking strategies. The first refers to when learners understand what they know, what they do not know what they desire to know. Meanwhile, awareness of thinking refers to learners' understanding the mental tasks that they need to accomplish to learn and what is required to complete these tasks. Lastly, awareness of thinking strategies pertains to when learners understand how direct learning should take place (Flavell 1979). Metacognitive knowledge enables learners use the information they possess about their cognition to direct or regulate their own learning for better outcomes. The ability of learners to demonstrate strategic thinking, evaluate their own strengths and weaknesses, set goals, organises ideas in a systematic and conceptual manner and solve problems is referred to as metacognitive regulation or executive control. Metacognition is important for learners to understand and regulate their own cognitive performance so that they can take total control of the way they learn.

1.4.3 Performance

Performance is the measurement of student achievement across various academic subjects. It is typically measured using classroom performance, graduation rates and results from standardised tests. Academic performance is defined as a student's ability to complete academic assignments. It is assessed using objective criteria such as final course grades and grading point average (Olivier et al. 2019:326-340). In this study, performance is the ability for learners to carry out acceptable translations of literary texts which demonstrate their mastery of adequate literary translation strategies and theories.

1.4.4 Translation

Translation is conceived as a process through which meaning, ideas, signs and emotions are rendered across languages aesthetically, accurately, clearly, and naturally. Catford (1965:20) defines translation as the replacement of textual material in one language by equivalent textual material in another language. Vinay and Darbelnet (1973:20) also define translation as an activity that takes place at the linguistic level as *‘le passage d’une langue A à une langue B, pour exprimer un même réel X’* [movement from language A to language B to express a similar reality, X]. Hence, to them, translation should entail faithful linguistic transfer, to the detriment of the communicative aspect of translation. Translation can be interlingual, intralingual or inter-semiotic (when it considers verbal and non-verbal translation).

1.4.5 Literary Translation

Boase-Beier (2011:46) defines literary translation as translation which considers the literary nature of a source text to create a target text which does justice to its stylistic features (iconicity and stylistic/rhetorical devices). Moreover, it is translation in which close attention is given not only to replicating the fictional world created by the source text author for the target audience, but also to ensuring the target text readers’ engagement and duplicating the cognitive state embodied in the source text into the target language. Therefore, literary translation is both the translation of literary texts and the translation of texts in a literary manner.

1.4.6 Literary Translation Learner

Literary translation is taught as a specialised translation course in literary translation at the Advanced School of Translators and Interpreters (ASTI) of the University of Buea. Thus, the term literary translation learner refers to student translators who take the above-mentioned course.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

This study is underpinned by Learning Theory, with emphasis on the tenets of Constructivism. The main thrust of Constructivism is that people learn by incorporating new ideas and understanding in their prior knowledge and experience. Therefore, since knowledge is created when new information is viewed through the lens of earlier experience, mental representations that help learners acquire new knowledge are very subjective. Learning takes place when learners make connections between prior knowledge and new ideas, hence each learner has a unique construction of knowledge. The theory is applied to explain how, on one hand, English A and on the other, French A students receive, process and retain knowledge differently during literary translation learning (Illeris 2004b). Specifically, it relies on constructivism to explain the assumption that French A learners’ ability to learn relies largely on their prior knowledge and understanding, whose acquisition is individually tailored through a process of construction. In other words, constructivism is applied to investigate how French A students construct new knowledge through experience and incorporate it with the knowledge they already possess as opposed to English A learners. Constructivism thus emphasises on the fact that it is important for learners to construct knowledge for themselves by using background knowledge and concepts that assist them in internalising new information. The main assumption here is that when learners receive new information, it creates confusion with their previous understanding and, therefore, requires them to adjust their cognitive structure to create a better cognitive schema than the one which has been distorted (Bodner et al. 2001:1107-1134).

2.0 Methodology

This section elucidates the methodology applied to this research, by spelling out the research design, sampling procedure and sample size, data elicitation procedure, method of data processing and analysis, validity/reliability of instruments as well as the ethical considerations that guide the study.

2.1 Research Design

The research design is a non-intervention case study. It entails an intensive, systematic investigation of two distinct groups of subjects that is conducted without making any attempt to change their behaviour.

2.2. Sampling Procedure

The sampling procedure is the non-probability sampling method, through which a population of 50 literary translation learners is selected. The aim of this sampling method is to study a small sample and generate a maximum amount of information. Thereafter, a pre-test is administered to this initial selection to eliminate outliers, out of which, one study group of 16 English A and another of 16 French A students are retained. The study population is composed of a homogenous sample of 32 literary translation students who scored from 15 to 17 on 20 in the selection test.

2.3 Data Elicitation Procedures

Qualitative and quantitative data for the study are culled through questionnaires and non-participant observation. The study elicits qualitative data associated with metacognition by administering to respondents Shraw & Denison's (1994:460-475) Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MIA), which comprises 52 declarations, out of which 17 declarations aim to investigate respondents' metacognitive knowledge and 35 to determine their metacognitive regulation. However, instead of true or false questions, in this study all 52 declarations to investigate responders' metacognitive knowledge and regulation are rephrased as questions to elicit responses designed on a 7-point Likert scale for frequency (never, rarely < 10%, occasionally 30%, sometimes 50%, frequently 70%, usually 90% and every time > 90%). Using this psychometric rating scale, responders specify the frequency with which they regulate cognition (by planning, managing information, monitoring understanding, correcting performance errors or self-evaluating) or demonstrate that they possess knowledge about cognition by establishing that they possess declarative, procedural or conditional knowledge. In addition to the MIA, a formative assessment test was administered to cull data about learners' performance in literary translation, whose outcome is used to compare the two groups.

2.3 Method of Data Processing and Analysis

Data collected from the close ended questions were first processed using the Excel Spreadsheet whereby, all participants' responses were coded and keyed. Instead of using the MIA scoring guide to generate raw data, related responses are summed together to get the trend of responses for each group of questions. After this process, the data from the close ended questions were exported into SPSS version 25 for further analysis. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation and inferential statistics (Independent Sample t-Test). The T-test was used to compare the metacognition test score of the students by language combination for significant difference. Lastly, the findings were presented on frequency distribution tables and on figures.

2.5 Validity and Reliability of Instruments

The MIA's reliability for this study is demonstrated through Cronbach's Alpha reliability analysis. This precise tool measures and elicits accurate responses and leaves little room for respondents to

digress from the required responses. Hence, both the data and instruments are reliable, given that they are consistent, as demonstrated in the following reliability analysis.

Table: 1
Reliability Analysis

Variables	Cronbach Coefficient Value	Alpha	Variance	No of valid Items
Metacognitive knowledge	.886		.116	17
Metacognitive regulation	.888		.209	35
Overall Reliability Coefficient	.887		.162	52

Statistics revealed that the internal consistency of all 32 participants was very satisfactory, with coefficient values that ranged from 0.886 to 0.888. The overall reliability coefficient value is 0.887, which is above the recommended threshold of 0.7.

2.5.1 Output of Reliability Analysis per Test Item

The case processing summaries of the output of reliability analysis for respondents' metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive regulation are presented in the following case processing summaries.

Metacognitive knowledge

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	32	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	32	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.887	.886	17

Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Variances	1.656	1.055	2.547	1.492	2.414	.116	17

Item-Total Statistics

Items	Scale Mean	Scale Variance	Cronbach's Alpha
How often do you ask yourself if you are meeting your goals?	79.94	151.480	.879
How often do you consider several alternatives to a problem before you answer?	80.31	157.577	.886
How often do you try to use strategies that have worked in the past?	79.75	153.742	.880

How often do you pace yourself while learning in order to have enough time?	80.22	162.628	.889
How often do you understand your intellectual strengths and weaknesses?	80.09	151.701	.887
How often do you think about what you really need to learn before you begin a task?	80.00	144.968	.876
How often do you know your performance after finishing a test?	80.13	148.113	.876
How often do you set specific goals before you begin a task?	80.34	149.265	.878
How often do you slow down when you encounter an important information?	80.31	150.157	.878
How often do you know what kind of information is most important to learn?	79.94	148.125	.876
How often do you ask yourself if you have considered all options when solving a problem?	80.47	156.838	.886
How good are you at organising information?	80.06	149.544	.877
How often do you consciously focus your attention on important information?	79.72	143.499	.870
How often do you have a specific purpose for each strategy that you use?	80.34	153.265	.881
How often do you learn best when you know something about the topic?	79.59	148.959	.879
How often do you know what the teacher expects you to learn?	80.56	156.706	.885
How often do you remember information?	80.22	154.241	.884

Metacognitive regulation

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	32	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	32	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.885	.888	35

Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Variances	1.739	.964	2.952	1.988	3.063	.209	35

Item-Total Statistics

Items	Scale Mean	Scale Variance	Cronbach's Alpha
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How often do you use learning strategies depending on the situation?	171.53	406.773	.879
How often do you ask yourself if there were an easier way to do things after you finish a task?	171.38	397.274	.879
How often do you have control over how well you learn?	171.47	404.128	.878
How often do you review to help yourself understand important relationships?	170.75	407.871	.880
How often do you ask yourself questions about the material before you begin?	171.28	393.112	.877
How often do you think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one?	170.88	404.113	.879
How often do you summarise what you've learned after you finish?	171.34	418.362	.885
How often do you ask others for help when you don't understand something?	170.84	426.523	.888
How often do you motivate yourself to learn when you need to?	170.81	417.448	.884
How often are you aware of what strategies to use when you study?	171.53	420.580	.885
How often do you find yourself analysing the usefulness of strategies while you study?	172.09	410.733	.881
How often do you use your intellectual strength to compensate your weakness?	170.56	418.060	.885
How often do you focus on the meaning and significance of new information?	171.09	406.410	.881
How often do you create your own examples to make information more meaningful?	171.09	405.830	.879
How often you correctly judge if you understand something well?	170.66	405.072	.880
How often do you find yourself using helpful learning strategies automatically?	171.25	411.226	.882
How often do you find yourself pausing to check your comprehension?	171.03	400.999	.879
How often do you know when each strategy you use will be most effective?	171.50	420.452	.884
How often do you ask yourself how well you accomplish your goals once you've finished?	171.28	400.209	.879
How often do you draw pictures and diagrams to help you understand while learning?	172.47	419.096	.888
How often do you ask yourself if you've considered all options after solving a problem?	171.81	410.996	.883
How often do you try to translate new information into your own words?	170.84	399.555	.877
How often do you change strategies when you fail to understand?	170.91	411.120	.881
How often do you use the organisational structure of the text to help you learn?	171.56	413.673	.884
How often do you carefully read instructions before beginning a task?	170.03	407.451	.880
How often do you ask yourself if what you're reading is related to what you already know?	170.69	399.190	.879
How often do you re-evaluate your assumptions when you get confused?	170.72	410.015	.880
How often do you organise your time to best accomplish your goals?	170.56	408.512	.882

How often do you learn when you're interested in the topic?	170.31	415.448	.883
How often do you try to break studying down into smaller steps?	171.31	405.125	.882
How often do you focus on overall meaning rather than specifics?	170.91	429.184	.887
How often do you ask yourself questions about how well you're doing while learning something new?	171.00	400.581	.879
How often do you ask yourself if you learned as much as you could have you finish a task?	171.22	403.080	.880
How often do you stop and go back over new information that is not clear?	170.53	417.483	.884
How often do you stop and reread when you get confused?	169.94	423.867	.885

2.6 Ethical Considerations

To guard against ethical issues in relation to this study, respondents were informed that the research was for purely academic purposes and that the results will not be monetised for the benefits of any of the stakeholders of the research. In addition, they are made aware of the common criterion for selecting participants in this study, which is that they are all student translators involved in literary translation learning in a common course. Also, they are informed that their responses in this questionnaire are entirely voluntary, and that they may refuse to answer any or all the questions if they feel uncomfortable. Moreover, they informed that agreeing to fill and return the questionnaire, they were giving their consent for their answers to be analysed and used in this research. Above all, they were reassured that all responses will be anonymised, and there will be no way to trace their answers back to them. Lastly, they were told that they will not be receiving any remuneration in return for their time by agreeing to participate in this study. The researcher's email address was also included in the questionnaire to address any concerns or questions about respondents' rights as participants in this study.

3.0 Presentation of Findings

This study set out to investigate if French A literary translation students at ASTI are more intentional in learning than English A students by selecting a sample of 32 students distributed per language combination as on the table below:

Figure: 1

Distribution of Students by Language Combination

Out of the 32 students sampled for the study, the language combination for 50.0% (16) is French A - English B and that for another 50.0% (16) is English A – French B.

3.1 Objective One: To investigate the degree of metacognitive awareness of the study population of literary translation learners in general.

Table: 2

Students' Frequency of Application of Metacognitive Knowledge in Learning

Questions about subjects' metacognition	Frequency of application of metacognitive knowledge in learning							
	Never (<5%)	Rarely (<10%)	Occasionally (30%)	Sometimes (50%)	Frequently (70%)	Usually (90%)	Every time (100%)	
How often do you ask yourself if you are meeting your goals?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (12.5%)	3 (9.4%)	13 (40.6%)	7 (21.9%)	5 (15.6%)	
How often do you consider several alternatives to a problem before you answer?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (18.8%)	6 (18.8%)	10 (31.3%)	8 (25.0%)	2 (6.3%)	
How often do you try to use strategies that have worked in the past?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	5 (15.6%)	9 (28.1%)	11 (34.4%)	5 (15.6%)	
How often do you pace yourself while learning in order to have enough time?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	9 (28.1%)	14 (43.8%)	4 (12.5%)	3 (9.4%)	
How often do you understand your intellectual strengths and weaknesses?	1 (3.1%)	1 (3.1%)	3 (9.4%)	8 (25.0%)	3 (9.4%)	10 (31.3%)	6 (18.8%)	
How often do you think about what you really need to learn	1 (3.1%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (9.4%)	6 (18.8%)	9 (28.1%)	6 (18.8%)	7 (21.9%)	

before you begin a task?							
How often do you know your performance after finishing a test?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (15.6%)	5 (15.6%)	12 (37.5%)	5 (15.6%)	5 (15.6%)
How often do you set specific goals before you begin a task?	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.1%)	5 (15.6%)	7 (21.9%)	10 (31.3%)	5 (15.6%)	4 (12.5%)
How often do you slow down when you encounter an important information?	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.1%)	3 (9.4%)	11 (34.4%)	6 (18.8%)	8 (25.0%)	3 (9.4%)
How often do you know what kind of information is most important to learn?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (12.5%)	6 (18.8%)	8 (25.0%)	8 (25.0%)	6 (18.8%)
How often do you ask yourself if you have considered all options when solving a problem?	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	1 (3.1%)	13 (40.6%)	9 (28.1%)	4 (12.5%)	3 (9.4%)
How good are you at organising information?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (12.5%)	8 (25.0%)	6 (18.8%)	10 (31.3%)	4 (12.5%)
How often do you consciously focus your attention on important information?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (9.4%)	5 (15.6%)	9 (28.1%)	6 (18.8%)	9 (28.1%)
How often do you have a specific purpose for each strategy that you use?	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.1%)	3 (9.4%)	9 (28.1%)	11 (34.4%)	5 (15.6%)	3 (9.4%)
How often do you learn best when you know something about the topic?	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.1%)	1 (3.1%)	6 (18.8%)	7 (21.9%)	6 (18.8%)	11 (34.4%)
How often do you know what the teacher expects you to learn?	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	4 (12.5%)	8 (25.0%)	11 (34.4%)	6 (18.8%)	1 (3.1%)
How often do you remember information?	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.1%)	3 (9.4%)	8 (25.0%)	8 (25.0%)	7 (21.9%)	4 (12.5%)
Total Response	2 (0.4%)	10 (1.8%)	56 (10.3%)	124 (22.8%)	155 (28.5%)	116 (21.3%)	81 (14.9%)

The overall findings showed that 0.4% of the students never apply metacognitive knowledge in learning, while 1.8% rarely apply it, 10.3% occasionally apply it, 22.8% sometimes apply it, 28.5% frequently apply it, 21.3% usually apply it and 14.9% apply it every time. Specifically, only 3.1% (1) of the students never understand their intellectual strengths and weaknesses often and think about what they really need to learn before beginning a task. Also, 3.1% (1) rarely understand their intellectual strengths and weaknesses, set specific goals before beginning a task, slow down when they encounter important information, have a specific purpose for each strategy that they use, learn best when know something about the topic and remember information. Furthermore, with reference to those who occasionally apply metacognitive knowledge in learning, 18.8% (6) of the students occasionally consider several alternatives to a problem before they answer, 15.6% (5) occasionally know their performance after finishing a test and set specific goals before the beginning of a task.

Again, 12.5% (4) of equal weight occasionally ask themselves if they are meeting their goals, know the kind of information that is important to learn, are good at organising information and know what the teacher expects them to learn. Furthermore, 9.4% (3) occasionally understand their intellectual strengths and weaknesses and think about what they really need to learn before beginning a task. With reference to the application of metacognitive knowledge in learning sometimes, 40.6% (13) sometimes asked themselves if they have considered all options before solving a problem, 34.4% (11) sometimes slow down when they encounter important information. Moreover, 28.1% (9) sometimes pace themselves while learning to have enough time, 25.0% (8) sometimes are good at organising information, know what teacher expects them to learn, remember information, and understand their intellectual strengths and weaknesses. Furthermore, between 21.6% (7) to 18.8% (6) sometimes set specific goals before beginning a task, think about what is really matters to learn before beginning a task, and learn best when they know something about the topic.

Furthermore, based on frequent, usually and every time application of metacognitive knowledge to learning, 43.8% (14) frequently pace themselves while learning to have enough time, while 21.9% (7) do that usually and 15.6% (5) every time. Again, 40.6% (13) frequently ask themselves if they are meeting their goals while 25.0% (8) does that usually and 6.3% (2) do it every time. Similarly, 37.5% (12) of the students frequently know their performance after finishing a task, while 15.6% (5) know that usually and every time. Again, 34.4% (11) frequently know what their teacher expects from them, while 18.8% (6) usually know it and only 3.1% (1) know it every time. In the same vein, 31.1% (10) of the students frequently set specific goals before beginning a task while 15.6% (5) do that usually and 12.5% (4) do it every time. Again, 28.1% (9) frequently try to use strategies that have worked in the past, while 34.4% (11) usually do it and 15.6% (5) do it every time. Lastly, 21.9% (7) frequently learn best when they know something about a topic while 18.8% (6) do that usually and 34.4% (11) do it every time.

Table: 3

Students' Frequency of Application of Metacognitive Regulation in Learning

Questions about subjects' metacognition	Frequency of application of metacognitive regulation in learning							
	Never (<5%)	Rarely (<10%)	Occasionally (30%)	Sometimes (50%)	Frequently (70%)	Usually (90%)	Every time (100%)	
How often do you use learning strategies depending on the situation?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (12.5%)	12 (37.5%)	11 (34.4%)	4 (12.5%)	1 (3.1%)	
How often do you ask yourself if there were an easier way to do things after you finish a task?	1 (3.1%)	2 (6.3%)	2 (6.3%)	9 (28.1%)	9 (28.1%)	4 (12.5%)	5 (15.6%)	
How often do you have control over how well you learn?	1 (3.1%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	10 (31.3%)	13 (40.6%)	6 (18.8%)	0 (0.0%)	
How often do you review to help yourself understand important relationships?	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.1%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (21.9%)	9 (28.1%)	9 (28.1%)	6 (18.8%)	
How often do you ask yourself questions about the material	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	2 (6.3%)	7 (21.9%)	6 (18.8%)	9 (28.1%)	4 (12.5%)	

before you begin?							
How often do you think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one?	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (18.8%)	9 (28.1%)	11 (34.4%)	4 (12.5%)
How often do you summarise what you've learned after you finish?	0 (0.0%)	3 (9.4%)	2 (6.3%)	8 (25.0%)	9 (28.1%)	7 (21.9%)	3 (9.4%)
How often do you ask others for help when you don't understand something?	1 (3.1%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	6 (18.8%)	6 (18.8%)	12 (37.5%)	5 (15.6%)
How often do you motivate yourself to learn when you need to?	1 (3.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (15.6%)	13 (40.6%)	8 (25.0%)	5 (15.6%)
How often are you aware of what strategies to use when you study?	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.1%)	5 (15.6%)	13 (40.6%)	3 (9.4%)	8 (25.0%)	2 (6.3%)
How often do you find yourself analysing the usefulness of strategies while you study?	0 (0.0%)	3 (9.4%)	9 (28.1%)	10 (31.3%)	5 (15.6%)	5 (15.6%)	0 (0.0%)
How often do you use your intellectual strength to compensate your weakness?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (12.5%)	3 (9.4%)	7 (21.9%)	8 (25.0%)	10 (31.3%)
How often do you focus on the meaning and significance of new information?	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	2 (6.3%)	7 (21.9%)	10 (31.3%)	5 (15.6%)	6 (18.8%)
How often do you create your own examples to make information more meaningful?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (12.5%)	7 (21.9%)	9 (28.1%)	9 (28.1%)	3 (9.4%)
How often you correctly judge if you understand something well?	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (9.4%)	5 (15.6%)	7 (21.9%)	9 (28.1%)	8 (25.0%)
How often do you find yourself using helpful learning strategies automatically?	1 (3.1%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	10 (31.3%)	9 (28.1%)	7 (21.9%)	3 (9.4%)
How often do you find yourself pausing to check your comprehension?	1 (3.1%)	1 (3.1%)	2 (6.3%)	4 (12.5%)	11 (34.4%)	9 (28.1%)	4 (12.5%)
How often do you know when each strategy you use will be most effective?	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.1%)	3 (9.4%)	11 (34.4%)	12 (37.5%)	3 (9.4%)	2 (6.3%)
How often do you ask yourself how well you accomplish your goals once you've finished?	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.3%)	4 (12.5%)	7 (21.9%)	9 (28.1%)	5 (15.6%)	5 (15.6%)
How often do you draw pictures and diagrams to help you understand while learning?	3 (9.4%)	6 (18.8%)	7 (21.9%)	8 (25.0%)	3 (9.4%)	2 (6.3%)	3 (9.4%)
How often do you ask yourself	0	2	10	7	7	2	4

if you've considered all options after solving a problem?	(0.0%)	(6.3%)	(31.3%)	(21.9%)	(21.9%)	(6.3%)	(12.5%)
How often do you try to translate new information into your own words?	0	1	1	6	11	7	6
How often do you change strategies when you fail to understand?	(0.0%)	(3.1%)	(3.1%)	(18.8%)	(34.4%)	(21.9%)	(18.8%)
How often do you use the organisational structure of the text to help you learn?	0	1	1	6	12	7	5
How often do you carefully read instructions before beginning a task?	(0.0%)	(3.1%)	(3.1%)	(18.8%)	(37.5%)	(21.9%)	(15.6%)
How often do you ask yourself if what you're reading is related to what you already know?	1	1	6	9	5	7	3
How often do you re-evaluate your assumptions when you get confused?	(3.1%)	(3.1%)	(18.8%)	(28.1%)	(15.6%)	(21.9%)	(9.4%)
How often do you organise your time to best accomplish your goals?	0	0	1	3	4	9	15
How often do you learn when you're interested in the topic?	(0.0%)	(0.0%)	(3.1%)	(9.4%)	(12.5%)	(28.1%)	(46.9%)
How often do you try to break studying down into smaller steps?	1	0	3	4	5	11	8
How often do you focus on overall meaning rather than specifics?	(3.1%)	(0.0%)	(9.4%)	(12.5%)	(15.6%)	(34.4%)	(25.0%)
How often do you ask yourself questions about how well you're doing while learning something new?	0	0	1	6	10	10	5
How often do you ask yourself if you learned as much as you could have you finish a task?	(0.0%)	(0.0%)	(3.1%)	(18.8%)	(31.3%)	(31.3%)	(15.6%)
How often do stop and go back over new information that is not clear?	0	0	4	3	7	8	10
How often do you stop and reread when you get confused?	(0.0%)	(0.0%)	(12.5%)	(9.4%)	(21.9%)	(25.0%)	(31.3%)
Total Response	14	36	101	236	279	271	183
	(1.3%)	(3.2%)	(9.0%)	(21.1%)	(24.9%)	(24.2%)	(16.3%)

In summary, with reference to the application of metacognitive regulation in learning, 1.3% of the students never apply it, 3.2% rarely apply it, 9.0% occasionally apply it, 21.1% sometimes apply it, 24.9% frequently apply it, 24.2% usually apply it and 16.3% apply it every time. Specifically, and for instance, 3.1% (1) of the students never asked themselves if there were an easier way to do things after finishing a task while 6.3% (2) rarely and occasionally do it, 28.1% sometimes and frequently do it, 12.5% (4) usually do it and 15.6% (5) do it every time. Also, 3.1% (1) never have control of how well they need to study while 6.3% (2) occasionally have such control, 31.3% (10) sometimes, 40.6% (13) frequently, 18.8% (6) usually and none every time. Again, 3.1% (1) of the students rarely review themselves to understand important relationships while 21.9% (7) do that sometimes, 28.1% (9) frequently and usually and 18.8% (6) every time. Again, 6.3% (4) of the students rarely and occasionally ask themselves questions about materials before beginning a task while 21.9% (7) do it sometimes, 18.8% (6) frequently, 28.1% (9) usually and 12.5% (4) every time. Furthermore, 6.3% (2) rarely think of several ways to solve a problem while 18.8% (6) do such sometimes, 28.1% (9) frequently, 34.4% (11) usually and 12.5% (4) every time. Similarly, 9.4% (3) of the students rarely summarized what they have learned after finishing a task while 6.3% (2) do it occasionally, 25.0% (8) sometimes, 28.1% (9) frequently, 21.9% (7) usually and 9.4% (3) every time. Again, 3.1% (1) of the students never ask others for help when they do not understand while 6.3% (2) do that occasionally, 18.8% (6) sometimes and frequently, 37.5% (12) usually and 15.6% (5) every time. Again, 3.1% (1) of students never motivate themselves while 15.6% (5) do it sometimes, 40.6% (13) frequently, 25.0% (8) usually and 15.6% (5) every time. Lastly, half of the students, 3.1% (1) of the students occasionally and sometimes stop to reread when they get confused while 18.8% (6) do it frequently, 25.0% (8) usually and 50.0% (16) every time.

Figure: 2
Showing in Summary the Frequency of Application of Metacognitive Awareness in Learning by the Students

In all, 1.0% of the students never apply metacognitive awareness in learning, 2.8% rarely apply it, 9.4% occasionally apply it, 21.6% sometimes apply it, 26.1% frequently apply it, 23.3% usually apply it and 15.9% apply it every time.

3.2 Objective Two: To find out if there are any differences in metacognitive awareness and performance in the groups of literary translation learners based on language combination.

Table: 3

Distribution of Students by Frequency of Application of Metacognitive Awareness in Learning by Language Combination

Language combination	Frequency of application of metacognitive awareness in learning							Total based on total response
	Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Sometimes	Frequently	Usually	Every time	
French A- English B	n 8	26	99	213	225	146	115	832
	% 1.0%	3.1%	11.9%	25.6%	27.0%	17.5%	13.8%	
English A- French B	n 8	20	58	147	209	241	149	832
	% 1.0%	2.4%	7.0%	17.7%	25.1%	29.0%	17.9%	
Total	n 16	46	157	360	434	387	264	1664

***Percentages and totals are based on responses.*

Findings showed that there are some differences in the frequency at which learners demonstrate metacognitive awareness in literary translation learning per language combination. More of the students with language combination French A- English B occasionally 11.9%, sometimes 25.6%, frequently 27.0% and every time 13.8% apply metacognitive awareness than the students with English A- French B. However, more of the students 29.0% with English A - French B only, usually apply metacognitive awareness against 17.5% for those with French A- English B.

3.3 Verification of Hypotheses

The two hypotheses stipulated at the beginning are as follows:

H1: There is a high degree of metacognitive awareness in the class of literary translation learners in general.

H2: French A literary translation learners do not significantly demonstrate a difference in metacognitive awareness from their English A counterparts.

3.3.1 Verification of Hypothesis One:

The degree of metacognitive awareness was measured using mean score generated from the students' frequency application of metacognitive awareness in learning.

Table: 4

Decision Level of Judge Students Application of Metacognitive Awareness in Learning

Frequency of application of metacognitive awareness	Scale	Decision level
Never	1	Very low
Rarely	2	
Occasionally	3	Low
Sometimes	4	Moderate
Frequently	5	High
Usually	6	

Every time	7	Very high
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Table: 5

Detail Mean Score on the Appraisal of Students' Application of Metacognitive Awareness in the Class of Literary Translation

Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Metacognitive knowledge			
How often do you ask yourself if you are meeting your goals?	32	4.19	1.203
How often do you consider several alternatives to a problem before you answer?	32	3.81	1.203
How often do you try to use strategies that have worked in the past?	32	4.38	1.129
How often do you pace yourself while learning in order to have enough time?	32	3.91	1.027
How often do you understand your intellectual strengths and weaknesses?	32	4.03	1.596
How often do you think about what you really need to learn before you begin a task?	32	4.13	1.476
How often do you know your performance after finishing a test?	32	4.00	1.270
How often do you set specific goals before you begin a task?	32	3.78	1.338
How often do you slow down when you encounter an important information?	32	3.81	1.281
How often do you know what kind of information is most important to learn?	32	4.19	1.306
How often do you ask yourself if you have considered all options when solving a problem?	32	3.66	1.234
How good are you at organising information?	32	4.06	1.268
How often do you consciously focus your attention on important information?	32	4.41	1.316
How often do you have a specific purpose for each strategy that you use?	32	3.78	1.211
How often do you learn best when you know something about the topic?	32	4.53	1.391
How often do you know what the teacher expects you to learn?	32	3.56	1.216
How often do you remember information?	32	3.91	1.304
Sub overall	32	4.00	1.280
Metacognitive regulation			
How often do you use learning strategies depending on the situation?	32	3.56	.982
How often do you ask yourself if there were an easier way to do things after you finish a task?	32	3.72	1.529
How often do you have control over how well you learn?	32	3.62	1.070

How often do you review to help yourself understand important relationships?	32	4.34	1.208
How often do you ask yourself questions about the material before you begin?	32	3.81	1.554
How often do you think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one?	32	4.22	1.263
How often do you summarise what you've learned after you finish?	32	3.75	1.391
How often do you ask others for help when you don't understand something?	32	4.25	1.391
How often do you motivate yourself to learn when you need to?	32	4.28	1.224
How often are you aware of what strategies to use when you study?	32	3.56	1.294
How often do you find yourself analysing the usefulness of strategies while you study?	32	3.00	1.218
How often do you use your intellectual strength to compensate your weakness?	32	4.53	1.367
How often do you focus on the meaning and significance of new information?	32	4.00	1.414
How often do you create your own examples to make information more meaningful?	32	4.00	1.191
How often you correctly judge if you understand something well?	32	4.44	1.294
How often do you find yourself using helpful learning strategies automatically?	32	3.84	1.298
How often do you find yourself pausing to check your comprehension?	32	4.06	1.413
How often do you know when each strategy you use will be most effective?	32	3.59	1.103
How often do you ask yourself how well you accomplish your goals once you've finished?	32	3.81	1.447
How often do you draw pictures and diagrams to help you understand while learning?	32	2.62	1.718
How often do you ask yourself if you've considered all options after solving a problem?	32	3.28	1.464
How often do you try to translate new information into your own words?	32	4.25	1.244
How often do you change strategies when you fail to understand?	32	4.19	1.203
How often do you use the organisational structure of the text to help you learn?	32	3.53	1.502
How often do you carefully read instructions before beginning a task?	32	5.06	1.134
How often do you ask yourself if what you're reading is related to what you already know?	32	4.41	1.500
How often do you re-evaluate your assumptions when you get confused?	32	4.38	1.070

How often do you organise your time to best accomplish your goals?	32	4.53	1.367
How often do you learn when you're interested in the topic?	32	4.78	1.157
How often do you try to break studying down into smaller steps?	32	3.78	1.560
How often do you focus on overall meaning rather than specifics?	32	4.19	1.120
How often do you ask yourself questions about how well you're doing while learning something new?	32	4.09	1.400
How often do you ask yourself if you learned as much as you could have you finish a task?	32	3.87	1.431
How often do stop and go back over new information that is not clear?	32	4.56	1.190
How often do you stop and reread when you get confused?	32	5.16	1.051
Sub overall	32	4.03	1.307
Grand overall mean	32	4.02	1.299

Table: 6

Summary of Mean Score on Appraisal of Students' Application of Metacognitive Awareness in the Class of Literary Translation

Metacognitive awareness	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Metacognitive knowledge	32	4.00	1.280
Metacognitive regulation	32	4.03	1.307
Overall mean	32	4.02	1.299

Findings showed on a mean scale of 1-7, the overall mean scored by the students is 4.02 which is moderate. Specifically, the sub mean value for metacognitive knowledge is 4.00 and 4.03 for metacognitive regulation which are not high on a scale of 1 to 7. Based on this, the hypothesis that states that there is a high degree of metacognitive awareness in the class of literary translation learners in general was rejected.

3.3.2 Verification of Hypothesis Two:

Table: 7

Tests of Normality

	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	p-value
Metacognitive test score	.941	32	.080

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Statistics from the test of normality showed that the metacognitive score of the students approximately follows the normal distribution pattern ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$). The Shapiro-Wilk test was used because the sample size is less than 50. Therefore, the second hypothesis of the study was verified using a parametric Independent Sample t-Test.

Table: 8*Comparing the Students' Metacognition test score by Language Combination*

	Language combination	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	T-test value	p-value
Metacognition test score	French A	16	13.19	2.2867	.5717	1.733	.093
	English B						
	English A	16	11.69	2.6005	.6501		
	French B						

df=30, equal variance assumed (Levene's Test for Equality of Variances; $F = .708$, p -value .407)

The findings showed that the students do not significantly differ in their metacognition test score by language combination (t- test value 1.733, p -value 0.093 > 0.5). Therefore, the hypothesis that states French A literary translation learners do not significantly demonstrate a different in metacognitive awareness from their English A counterparts was accepted.

4.0 Conclusion

This study set out to investigate metacognitive awareness of literary translation learners at ASTI. It started from the assumption that there is a generally high degree of metacognitive awareness in the literary translation class, which is not predicated on language combination. From the results of the data analysis, this hypothesis was rejected, for it was revealed that all the students do not possess the ability to predict how well they learn. Based on the foregoing, this study makes recommendations to two stakeholders, namely to students and to teachers.

Since the findings demonstrated that French A learners are more metacognitively aware than English A learners, the study recommended that the latter should adopt some strategies, such as reflecting on which study resources to use, why these resources are useful, and how they will use them, to enable them to enhance their metacognitive abilities. By so doing, English A learners will be on the par with their French A counterparts. It also recommended that both groups of learners should adopt innovative learning strategies that will lead them to have an enhanced self-reflection and cognitive control that will both work in favour of their ability to predict how well they can perform literary translation tasks.

Concerning literary translation teachers, the study recommended that they should understand and consider the inherent differences between learners in the literary translation classroom and ensure that their methods accommodate the less metacognitively aware group in the class. If this is done, trainers will be able to maximise the learning experience and outcomes for both French A and English A students. Also, teachers should teach literary translation learner's strategies that will make them gain greater awareness of their metacognitive abilities.

The implication of this study to literary translation teaching is that it will lay greater emphasis on enhancing students' metacognitive competence to boost learners' confidence about their learning. That is, teachers should provide learners with more opportunities to engage in real-world literary translation projects that will test their metacognitive knowledge as an integral part of their training. Notwithstanding the diverse nature of the classroom with students who have different languages and consequently different cultures, through the right teaching strategies, the congruence between the two groups of subjects should be increased while the disparity between them should be reduced. To conclude, there is need for more research that involves a larger sample of participants in other courses to explore the dynamics of learning translation by developing greater understanding of metacognition.

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